

Benzothieno (2,3-*d*) Thiazolo (3, 2-*a*) Pyrimidines

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Some benzothieno (2, 3-*d*) thiazolo (3, 2-*a*) pyrimidines with various substitutions in position 2 have been synthesised to evaluate these compounds for antibacterial activity. The structure has been confirmed on the basis of analytical results, IR and NMR studies.

RECENT communication¹ from this laboratory described the synthesis of thiazolo(3,2-*a*)thieno(2,3-*d*) pyrimidines. It was thought that fusion of another cyclic structure in this system would be of great interest. So in this communication, we report the synthesis of benzothieno(2,3-*d*)thiazolo(3,2-*a*)pyrimidines.

These compounds have been synthesised by the condensation of 2-amino-3-carbethoxy-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzothiophene(I) with allyl isothiocyanate(II). Isothiourea derivative(III) thus formed, on treatment with dry hydrochloric acid gas resulted in the formation of 2,3,6,7,8,9-hexahydro-2-methyl 5*H*(I)benzothieno(2,3-*d*) thiazolo (3,2-*a*)pyrimidin-5-one(IV).

The structure of both III as well IV has been confirmed on the basis of NMR. NMR* of III showed two multiplets at 7.25 and 8.24 (4H each) assignable

a three proton triplet at 8.64 (-CH₂-CH₃). The two proton quartet (-CH₂-CH₃) and multiplet for two allylic protons (-CH₂-CH=CH₂) merged to give a multiplet at 5.4-5.9. [Similarly the multiplet for two non-equivalent

vinyl protons () and multiplet for one

vinyl proton and the signal due to NH overlapped to give a multiplet for 4H at 3.5-4.8.

NMR of IV showed two multiplets each of four proton intensity at 7.20 and 8.20 due to methylene protons of tetrahydrobenzo moiety. Methyl protons (3H; -HC-CH₃) attached to thiazolidine ring appeared as doublet at 8.42 while the multiplets for one proton (-CH₂-CH-CH₃) and two non-equivalent protons (-CH₂-C₁H-) overlapped and gave a multiplet at 5.4-6.1.

The intermediate III, on treatment with bromine in chloroform gave rise to 2,3,6,7,8,9-hexahydro-2-bromo-

methyl 5*H*(1) benzothieno (2,3-*d*) thiazolo (3,2-*a*) pyrimidin-5-one(V). NMR of V showed two multiplets at 7.15 and 8.10 (4H each). Two non-equivalent protons

(-CH-CH₂Br) appeared as multiplet at 6.3. It also showed a multiplet at 5.35 assignable to two non-equivalent protons (-CH₂-CH-) and a multiplet at 5.70

at 4.7 (2H, -CH₂-CH=CH₂) and the other at 4.32 (2H, -CH₂-CH=CH₂). The structure VI gets further confirmation by the presence of exocyclic methylene band (at 890 cm⁻¹. Subsequent bromination

of VI converted it into 2,3,6,7,8,9-hexahydro-2-bromo-2-bromomethyl 5*H*(1) benzothieno (2, 3-*d*) thiazolo (3, 2-*a*) pyrimidin-5-one(VII). The whole scheme may be depicted as follows :

* Chemical shifts throughout the paper in τ (ppm).

The structure of the various compounds has further been confirmed on the basis of analytical results, I.R. and from our previous observation¹.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open glass capillaries in paraffin liquid bath and are uncorrected. I. R. spectra were taken in Nujol on Perkin Elmer grating I. R. spectrophotometer 621 and NMR spectra of III, IV and V on 60 MHz Varian spectrometer in CDCl_3 using TMS as internal indicator and that of VI in TFA.

Condensation of 2-amino-3-carbethoxy-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzothiophene with allyl isothiocyanate i.e. isolation of N-allyl 2N'-(3-Carbethoxy-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzothienol)isothiourea (III) :

A mixture of 2-amino-3-carbethoxy-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzothiophene² (2.25 g; 0.01 mole) and allyl isothiocyanate (0.99 g; 0.01 mole) was heated on a water bath. The contents first became mobile after half an hour and then solidified. It was heated for 6 hours in all. The product was triturated with a little of ethanol and filtered. Crystallisation from ethanol gave the isothiourea (III) (2.40 g, 74%) as yellow plates m.p. 52°; (Found: C, 56.02; H, 6.60; N, 8.58. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}_2$ requires C, 55.55; H, 6.17; N, 8.64%).

2,3,6,7,8,9-hexahydro-2-methyl-5H(1)benzothieno(2,3-d)thiazolo(3,2-a)pyrimidin-5-one (IV) :

Dry hydrochloric acid gas was passed through a refluxing solution of isothiourea derivative III (3.24 g) in absolute ethanol (50 ml) for 4 hr. Ethanol was distilled off and the residue basified with 5% sodium carbonate solution. The product was collected under suction, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol into white needles of the pyrimidinone (IV) (2.20 g, 79%) m.p. 145°; ν , 1655 cm^{-1} ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$) (Found: C, 56.43; H, 5.52; N, 9.72. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{OS}_2$ requires C, 56.12; H, 5.04; N, 10.08%).

2,3,6,7,8,9-hexahydro-2-bromomethyl-5H(1)benzothieno(2,3-d)thiazolo(3,2-a)pyrimidin-5-one (V) :

A solution of bromine (0.5 ml; 0.01 mole) in chloroform (10 ml) was added dropwise to a solution of isothiourea derivative III (3.24 g; 0.01 mole) in 50 ml of the same solvent with constant stirring at 5°. The addition was complete in half an hour. The contents were kept at room temperature for 4 hr. by which time the colour of bromine had completely

disappeared. On evaporation of the solvent on a water bath was obtained the pyrimidinone (V) (2.70 g, 76%) m.p. 142° (ethanol); ν 1660 ($-\text{C}=\text{O}$) (Found: C, 43.98; H, 4.10; N, 7.35. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{13}\text{BrN}_2\text{OS}_2$ requires C, 43.69; H, 3.64; N, 7.84%).

2,3,6,7,8,9-Hexahydro-2-methylene-5H(1) benzothieno(2,3-d)thiazolo(3,2-a)pyrimidin-5-one (VI) :

To a solution of 2,3,6,7,8,9-hexahydro-2-bromomethyl-5H(1)benzothieno(2,3-d)thiazolo(3,2-a)pyrimidin-5-one (1 g) in 60% ethanol (50 ml) was added 2% ethanolic sodium hydroxide solution (60.5 ml) at 45°. The contents were maintained at this temperature for 20 minutes. After cooling it to room temperature, crushed ice (100 g) was added. The separated product was collected under suction and crystallised from ethanol into yellowish needles m.p. 184°; yield being 0.70g (91%). Found: N, 10.60; $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_2\text{OS}_2$ requires N, 10.14%. It gives a characteristic IR absorption band

at 890 cm^{-1} for exocyclic methylene ($>\text{C}=\text{CH}_2$).

2,3,6,7,8,9-hexahydro-2-bromo-2-bromomethyl-5H(1) benzothieno(2,3-d)thiazolo(3,2-a)pyrimidin-5-one (VII) :

A solution of bromine (0.2 ml) in carbon tetrachloride (5 ml) was added gradually to a solution of 2,3,6,7,8,9-hexahydro-2-methylene-5H(1)benzothieno(2,3-d)thiazolo(3,2-a)pyrimidin-5-one (1.10 g) in 30 ml of the same solvent at 5°. After the addition, the contents were left as such for 3 hr. when the colour of bromine was discharged. Carbon tetrachloride was evaporated when the pyrimidinone (VII) (1.46 g, 84%) m.p. 250° (acetone) was obtained. (Found: N, 6.81; $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{Br}_2\text{N}_2\text{OS}_2$ requires N, 6.42%).

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